

Communicative Approach – A way to develop English Language Skill of ESL Learners

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Abstract

Communicative Approach is one of the methods applied in English Language Teaching to develop the communication skill of the students. This approach makes the language class student centered and students have more chances to interact freely in the classroom. The importance of teaching English is to make the students communicate well and develop the Ready to Go Anywhere skill. In the present scenario how to teach English is a challenging one as students are weak in communication. They turn a deaf ear when English is spoken and taught. So language teachers are in the position of teaching students to develop their communication skills. Communicative Approach paved the way in developing communication skills among students. The outcome of education is not in graduating the students but in making them communicate with confidence. This research focuses on the advantages, challenges and methods involved in a communicative Approach.

Aims and Objectives

The Aims and objectives of the research are as follows:

1. To test the effectiveness of the communicative approach to develop English language skills among students.
2. To compare the effectiveness of communicative approach and traditional method of teaching.
3. To test the effectiveness of communicative approach by comparing the achievement of the students' English language skills in terms of immediate post-test achievement and variables like size, status of higher secondary education, economic status of parents, educational status of parents.
4. To study the practical difficulties in implementing the models of teaching in the class rooms and to collect creative suggestions for the effective implementation of the scheme.

Hypothesis

Learners will develop communication skill in English.

Learners will come out from fear of crowd.

Learners will understand the purpose of communicative approach.

Learners will develop self confidence.

Learner centered atmosphere will be in the classrooms.

Research Methodology

This chapter deals with the methodology of research carried out by the researcher. It also explain the sample chosen (random) of the study, the profile of the sample, the details of the experiment, the tools used and other related details.

Study Sample and Learner Profile

The sample for this experimental research had a minimum of 100 students of an institution. The sample includes students differing in programmes, interests in language learning, Socio economic, linguistic backgrounds with different level of motivation and levels of proficiency in English.

Sample Justification

A vast majority of the students do not have

communication skills in English.

These learners do not read newspapers or journals and not read in text books in the classrooms. They are not able to speak in English with their teachers or friends. They are very slow in writing and practice to write which are written on the black board. They are lacking in listening skills. But their aim for studying is to get a job and to develop communication skills in English.

Sample Details

The main participants of this study are students of B.A and B.Sc who learn English as the second language in their graduate level. The participants of this study are selected from the institution which is affiliated to Madurai Kamaraj University in Tamil Nadu State offers English as second language for the students in the first year and the second year Undergraduate level. The sample contains the experimental group and the Control Group.

Design of the Study

Stage-I A survey has been conducted using a questionnaire and a pre-test has been given to analyze their language skills. The pre-test has been assessed and the scores will be tabulated and recorded for analysis.

Stage-II: A unique curriculum has been designed using the principles of task based learning and teaching. The curriculum included materials of different types with different activities and tasks. Further it will be conducted in the Control Group for establishing the hypothesis that language skills could be achieved if Communicative Approach is applied.

Stage-III: A post test has been conducted and assessed. The scores have been analyzed for validation. The data thus collected has been used for analysis and for interpretation and deriving conclusions.

Expected Outcome(s)

The following are the expected outcome of the research:

A change in the method of teaching will enable the students not only acquire language skills but also

develop interest in the English language classroom.

If the approach is task based, then the student will develop language skills and thus acquire the required levels of language skills.

The experimental study will also include testing the effectiveness of the Task Based approach to develop communication skills for improving language of the students. It is thus proposed to have an experimental group of the students as samples for this research.

There will be a slight improvement between the Control Group and the Experimental Group.

The Experimental Group will enjoy and feel that developing Communication Skill is not much difficult.

Results and Discussions

Communicative Approach is different from other methods of teaching. In the post test if the students showed any improvement the communicative approach will be very effective to develop the communication skills of the students. If the students prefer a communicative approach that can be preferred in HEI in all semesters or else traditional methods can be followed.

Conclusion

What has been said or outlined in this research on approach will give 'Received information' and 'Received knowledge', mostly received from other scholars, theorists, teachers, etc. Such received knowledge can only give the basic framework or at least an awareness of the phenomenon. A real understanding comes only out of the teacher's own "live experience". It transforms knowledge into wisdom. Unless a teacher experiences the teaching - learning process as a joint venture in the classroom, he/she cannot find a method that is suitable for the situation. Normally a classroom situation is a human situation, consisting of human beings and human elements. Yesterday's class was different from today's class and tomorrow's class will be different from the next days. So there is no standard class or a standard prescription for teaching and learning or for methodology. Communicative Approach is a way to keep students away from the traditional way of learning in the ESL class rooms and will help the students to develop communication skills in HEI.

Recommendations

The study can be taken up on a large sample with the objective of promoting the use of communicative approach to develop English language skills of the rural students. The study can be extended with the objectives remaining the same with English for slow learners, problems faced by the slow learners in English language class rooms, problems faced by the learners in co-education institution while speaking in English in the language classes, problems in developing vocabulary skill, pronunciation and the challenges faced by the students while pronouncing words etc...

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